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for a healthy future

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Annex 2.2.3 to D7.3

SOP 3:

Procedure for obtaining human samples

WP7

Task 7.2

D 7.3

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1 Introduction

Human biomonitoring is a powerful tool in the field of public health, although the lack of harmonization among the different HBM studies/programs can considerably limit the comparison of results, their global interpretation and subsequent translation into policy actions. Thus, in order to make possible an efficient use of the results of HBM studies is necessary to build a harmonized framework covering all stages of the HBM studies.

This guideline is intended to be used in the framework of the Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU). HBM4EU has the aim to establish a European human biomonitoring platform and to fill knowledge gaps in representative exposure data. For the first year of the project a groups of substances have been selected: DINCH, phthalates, bisphenols, flame retardants, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), PAHs, cadmium, chromium and aromatic amines. Appendix 3.1 describes the biomarkers and matrices included in the QA/QC scheme of the HBM4EU and thus, those biomarkers that will be analysed in the ICI/EQUAS in 2018.

The Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for sampling provides an overview of the general procedure for the collection of human samples in human biomonitoring studies.

It is important to highlight that depending on the target chemical, additional treatments or precautions could be necessary. In addition, the definition of the minimum quantity of sample collected will depend on the amount required for subsequent chemical analysis which will in turn vary depending on the analytical method, the limit of quantification, etc. Therefore, these issues must be discussed previously and defined with the laboratory responsible for the analysis.

2 Precautions in the pre-analytical phase

The pre-analytical phase comprises all actions and aspects that occur prior to the analytical phase and should be considered as part of the laboratory works. This phase involves the sample collection, handling, transport and conservation, aliquoting and storage until the analysis.

Quality Control measures are commonly applied during the analytical phase by means of blanks, calibration curves, control samples, etc. in order to guarantee the reliability of their results. Control measures are often absent from the pre-analytical phase, however, all the precautions and controls measures taken during chemical analysis are useless if the samples have already been contaminated or altered during the previous steps such as sampling, transport or processing. Indeed, the pre-analytic phase has been identified as more error-prone than other intra and post-analytical steps^{1,2}

Control of the pre-analytical phase is even more important in human biomonitoring studies involving the general, supposedly non-exposed population than in other kinds of studies involving biological samples. On one hand, the type of samples analysed because when measuring an environmental chemical there is a risk of sample contamination due to the presence of this chemical in the environment. This is especially important in the case of ubiquitous chemicals that may even be present in the sampling material. On the other hand, the exposure to environmental chemicals usually occurs at low concentrations and their levels in biological matrices also tend to be low, thus meaning that the influence of a potential contamination on the results is high.

As such, it is essential to identify and avoid, or at least minimise, the possible sources of contamination. In this regard two main group of factors should be considered:

a) Influencing factors:

¹ Plebani M, et al. Performance criteria and quality indicators for the pre-analytical phase. *Clin Chem Lab Med.* 53:943-948. 2015.

² Plebani M. The detection and prevention of errors in laboratory medicine. *Ann Clin Biochem.* 47:101-110. 2010.

These factors are specific for each biomarker and are present before the sampling. The biological half-life of a chemical, alcohol consumption, medication intake or individual habits such as diet, are examples of influencing factors that can modify the levels of the chemical of interest. Therefore, the influencing factors for the target biomarker must be identified and a sampling strategy that takes them into account designed and finally considered during the results interpretation.

b) Interfering factors

These factors can modify the concentration of the biomarker after sampling due to different processes such as the external contamination, physical or chemical changes in the biomarker during transport or storage, or changes in the biological matrix (e.g. coagulation or sedimentation). In this case, it is essential to identify and avoid possible sources of contamination, such as exogenous contamination at the sampling location, contamination from the sampling equipment or vessels, or alterations due to absorption of the components to be analysed onto the walls of the vessel employed.

Although various different tools can be employed to control the pre-analytical phase, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) tend to be the most useful. A SOP is a clear, concise, comprehensive and detailed step-by-step written description of a sampling or recruitment procedure, analytical method, etc. Other control measures include the use of field blanks during fieldwork, the collection of replicate samples or the pre-cleaning of the sampling material or the control of the background contamination in sampling material.

The sampling SOP should also describe the measures for an unambiguous identification of the specimens and related documents (questionnaires, personal data, etc.) and conservation of the samples.

Finally, a written record of every event that occurs during sampling and all sample-related parameters (date and time of collection, volume, length, colour, etc.) will help in the identification of potential problems, for example, cross-contamination of a sample (e.g. urine sample contaminated with blood from menstruation). Additionally, a well-documented sampling procedure facilitates communication and avoids misunderstandings and errors within the fieldworkers' team and between fieldworkers and laboratory staff.

2.1 Urine

This biological matrix is the result of a filtration process that occurs in the kidneys to eliminate water-soluble toxins and waste from the body. Together with blood, urine is the biological matrix of choice in human biomonitoring studies as it is a non-invasive matrix, easy to collect and available in larger amounts than other matrices.

Spot urine samples are usually employed instead of 24-hour samples as the latter are more uncomfortable to collect and are more likely to become contaminated due to continuous opening of the vessel. When using spot urine samples, the variability in the volume of urine produced needs to be corrected since the concentration of endogenous and exogenous chemicals can vary significantly from void to void depending on the hydration status, time of last urination, etc. This dilution adjustment can be done by different methods, such as creatinine adjustment or specific gravity^{3, 4, 5}.

³ Cornellis R. et al. *Pure and Applied Chemistry*. 67:1575-1608.1995.

⁴ Barr DB. et al. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 113: 192-200. 2005.

⁵ Aitio A. & Jarvisalo J. *Pure and Applied Chemistry*. 56: 549-566. 1984.

Although spot urine samples can be collected at any time of day, a first morning urine sample is recommended as otherwise the target biomarker may be below the LOQ due to sample dilution. A further possibility is to collect samples after at least 5 hours without urination.

2.1.1 Material needed for urine collection and storage

1. Urine collection vessels (120 ml polypropylene with a screw cap, pretreated and per-screened, see Appendix 3.2)
2. Labels
3. Latex or similar gloves
4. Sampling instructions for volunteers (Appendix 3.3)
5. Field blanks (120 ml polypropylene with a screw cap pre-treated filled with ~80 ml of purified water and handled as the real samples)

2.1.2 Sampling questionnaire for urine

The urine sampling should be accompanied by the collection of some basic information related to the urine sample and relevant questions that are necessary for the data interpretation.

The sampling questionnaire for urine should collect the following information:

1. Date and time of urine collection
2. First morning urine or not
3. If applicable, reasons for not collecting the sample
4. Time of the last urinate before urine collection
5. Time of the last meal before urine collection
6. Type of food consumed within the last 24 hours previously to the urine collection: fish, seafood, canned food, food packed in paperboard container, food packed in plastic bag, dried food, etc.
7. Observations

2.2 Blood

Blood is an ideal matrix for most chemicals because it is in contact with all tissues and is in equilibrium with the organs and tissues where chemicals are deposited. The collection of blood samples requires trained sanitary staff, special precautions related to the handling of biological material and commonly it requires an insurance contracting. Contrary to the urine sampling, the volume of blood that can be collected is quite limited.

Different types of blood samples can be collected. Samples of whole blood require additives to prevent the coagulation and both plasma and serum are derived from full blood that has undergone different biochemical processes after blood collection.

2.2.1 Sampling material

The number and type of blood tubes will depend on different aspects among them the target chemicals, the number of analysis or the LOQ of the analytical method employed.

1. Extraction tubes[†]:
 - Blood and plasma samples: tubes with anticoagulant.
 - Serum samples: tubes with no additives.
2. Regular phlebotomy needle or butterfly needle
3. Alcohol prep pads or wipes
4. Labels

5. Latex or similar gloves
 6. Sampling instructions for the medical staff performing the phlebotomy (Appendix 3.4)
 7. Field blanks (tubes filled with purified water and handled as the real samples)
- * *For the analysis of trace elements special tubes should be used to minimised the background contamination, e.g. Vacuette® Trace Elements 6 ml.*

2.2.2 Sampling questionnaire for blood

The blood sampling should be accompanied by the collection of some basic information related to the blood sample and relevant questions that are necessary for the data interpretation.

The sampling questionnaire for blood should collect the following information:

1. Date and time of blood collection
2. Number of tubes collected
3. If applicable, reasons for not collecting the required samples
4. Time of the last meal before blood collection
5. Type of food consumed within the last 24 hours previously to the blood collection: fish, seafood, canned food, food packed in paperboard container, food packed in plastic bag, dried food, etc.
6. Observations

2.3 Conservation, transport and storage of the samples

The deliverable report *D.7.2 “Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands”* includes all information related to the proper conservation and transport of the samples in human biomonitoring studies as well as the conditions of storage until the chemical analysis.

3 Specific recommendations for the substances in the 1st list of prioritization

Table 1 shows some recommendations for the selected group of substances regarding the pre-analytical phase. For its elaboration, WP9 experts and the CGLs were consulted.

Table 1. Recommendations for the groups of substances in the 1st list of prioritisation.

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	Phthalates	DINCH	Bisphenols	FRs
Sampling material				
<i>To avoid</i>	- Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	- Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	- Polycarbonate (PC), polyethersulfone (PES), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), epoxy resins	–
<i>Preferred</i>	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)
<i>Pre-treatment</i>	- Wash with methanol - Decontamination with acid solution	–	–	- Material free of dust particles (rinse with methanol)
<i>Additives</i>	- No	- No	- No	- No
<i>Risk of contamination</i>	- Low/medium	- Low	- Low/medium	- Medium/high
<i>Precautions to minimize contamination</i>	- Precaution with non-oxidized monoester metabolites (MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP; MnPeP, MEHP, MnOP): take sampling blanks to account for onsite background values. - SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material.	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of field blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- Avoid the use of polystyrene (PS) packaging boxes - Be aware of dust as major source of contamination - SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks
Transport & conservation				
<i>Shipment</i>	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen If not cooling, not longer than 72h	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen If not cooling, not longer than 72h	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen - - Avoid transport in polystyrene (PS) packaging boxes
<i>Biobank</i>	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	- Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C Preferred - Avoid polystyrene (PS) boxes
Related questions				
<i>Medical treatment</i>	- Are you taking medication in plastic capsules? - Please list the medications used - Dialysis, blood transfusion, blood donations (prior 24h)	- Are you taking medication in plastic capsules? - Please list the medications used - Dialysis, blood transfusion, blood donations (prior 24h)	- Dental fillings and inlays	
<i>Diet</i>	- Fasting period in the last 24h - Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	- Fasting period in the last 24h - Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	- Are you eating regularly canned food?/ Are you drinking regularly beverages canned? - Last meal eating canned food/beverages	Fatty fish consumption (BFRs)

			- Please mention if the food was packed and/or warmed in plastic containers	
Others	-	-	-	- Occupation - Use of computer and electronic equipment * Note: FRs are a very diverse group and there is a large number of possible sources of exposure

Recommendations	Group of substances			
	PFAS	PAHs	Anilines	Cd & Cr
Sampling material				
<i>To avoid</i>	- Teflon (Polytetrafluoroethylene, PTFE) and other fluoropolymers, glass	-	-	- Glass and metal
<i>Preferred</i>	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Polypropylene (PP)	- Urine: Polypropylene (PP) - Blood: special tubes for trace elements analysis
<i>Pre-treatment</i>	- No	- No	-	Urine: wash sampling material with 10% solution of HNO ₃
<i>Additives</i>	- No	- No	- As precautionary measure, 0.5 g citric acid per 100 mL urine should added to each sample container to avoid absorption of MDA, 2,4-/2,6-TDA.	- EDTA or heparin
<i>Risk of contamination</i>	- Medium	- Low	- High for aniline and o-toluidine	- Medium
<i>Precautions to minimize contamination</i>	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks - Precaution with dust particles	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material, use of sampling blanks	- SOPs for sampling, test the background level in sampling material (including needles used in venipuncture), use of sampling blanks
Transport & conservation				
<i>Shipment</i>	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen	- Cooled (2-8°C) or frozen - Plasma: centrifugation and plasma removing is needed latest 24h after sampling - Red blood cells: centrifugation, plasma removing and three times washing with 0.9% NaCl solution is needed latest 24h after sampling

<i>Biobank</i>	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred	Frozen, -20°C minimum, -80°C preferred in PP material pre-treated with 10% solution of HNO ₃
Related questions				
<i>Medical treatment</i>	–	–	Recent use of acetaminophen, paracetamol, panodil	- Medication, contrast procedures in the pas 96h (Cr)
<i>Diet</i>	- Food eaten previous to the sampling - Consumption of microwave popcorn and packed fast food	- Barbeque	–	- Seafood consumption, canned food and drinks, vitamins and supplements containing Cr
<i>Others</i>	- Use of cosmetics, houseware, cleaning products, kitchen utensils, baking paper	- Smoking behaviour, black tattoos, traffic related exposure, occupational	- Smoking habits, occupational or environmental contact to isocyanate containing foams or glues and pesticides, hair dyes, tattoos.	- Smoking habits, occupation, piercing, jewellery, tattoos, implant, prothesis,

4 Appendix

4.1 Parameters included in the HBM4EU ICI/EQUAS 2018

SUBSTANCE GROUP	BIOMARKER	MATRIX
Phthalates	MEP	Urine
	MBzP	
	MiBP	
	MnBP	
	MCHP	
	MnPeP	
	MEHP	
	5OH-MEHP	
	5oxo-MEHP	
	5cx-MEPP	
	MnOP	
	OH-MiNP	
	cx-MiNP	
	OH-MiDP	
	cx-MiDP	
DINCH	OH-MINCH	Urine
	cx-MINCH	
Bisphenols	BPA	Urine
	BPF	
	BPS	
PFAS	PFPeA	Serum
	PFHxA	
	PFHpA	
	PFOA	
	PFNA	
	PFDA	
	PFUnDA	
	PFDoDA	
	PFBS	
	PFHxS	
	PFHpS	
	PFOS (sum of all isomers)	
	PAHs	
2-hydroxynaphthalene		
1,2-dihydroxynaphthalene		
2-hydroxyfluorene		
(2-FLUO)		
3-hydroxyfluorene (3-FLUO)		
9-hydroxyfluorene		
(9-FLUO)		

	1-hydroxyphenanthrene	
	2-hydroxyphenanthrene	
	3-hydroxyphenanthrene	
	4-hydroxyphenanthrene	
	9-hydroxyphenanthrene	
	1-hydroxypyrene (1-PYR)	
	3-hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene	
Flame retardants	BDE-47	Serum
	BDE-153	
	BDE-209	
	α-HBCD	
	γ-HBCD	
	DPHP	Urine
	BDCIPP	
	BCEP	
	BCIPP	
	TBBPA	Serum
	Syn-DP	
	Anti-DP	
	DBDPE	
	2,4,6-Tribromophenol	
Aromatic amines	MDA	Urine
	MOCA	
	Aniline	
	p-aminophenol	
	N-acetyl-4-aminophenol	
	p-PDA	
	o-toluidine	
	2,4-TDA	
	2,6-TDA	
	Metals	
Blood		
Chromium		Red blood cells (erythrocytes)
		Urine
		Plasma

4.2 Pre-treatment/pre-screening of the vessels for urine sampling

Urine vessels should be washed with 10% nitric acid in purified water solution in order to eliminate background contamination of metals. The detailed procedure is shown below:

1. Prepare a 10% nitric acid solution from nitric acid 65% extra pure and purified water.
2. Put the solution in a tank.
3. Open the vessels and put vessels and lids into the tank. Ensure that all of them are completely immersed.
4. Vessels should be immersed in this tank at least for 3 hours (preferably overnight).
5. Take out the vessels from the acid tank and put them in a first tank with purified water. Shake for 2-3 minutes. Then, change the vessels and lids to a second tank of purified water. Shake for 2-3 minutes.
6. Take out vessels and lids and put them face down in a clean filter paper in order to dry them.
7. Once the drying is finished, lids are screwed to the resulting nitric acid pre-treated vessels. It is useful to make a mark indicating the minimum amount of urine required. Then, put the pre-treated vessel into a zip-lock plastic bag (or similar) in order to be sent to the survey office.

The acid solution can be reused until one month after its preparation. All the procedure must be done in a chemical fume hood with the suitable personal protective equipment.

To control the presence of contaminants, 5% of all urine vessels (after the cleaning procedure) have to be randomly selected. For this purpose, the vessels have to be filled with 200 ml purified water, shaken for 10 minutes, and aliquot has to be analysed for the biomarkers in question.

It is advisable to perform this screening for all the target biomarkers in order to identify background contamination.

4.3 Instructions for urine sampling

Please read carefully these instructions before taking the urine sample and do not use other vessel than the one provided.

1. Go to the bathroom.
2. Wash your hands carefully.
3. Open the vessel and place the screw cap with the top side down to avoid external contamination from dust.
4. Discharge the urine in the vessel until filled at least $\frac{3}{4}$ or until the minimum mark.
5. Screw the cap on tight.
6. Keep the sample at 4-8°C until you give it to the healthcare staff. Do not freeze the sample.

Thank you very much for your cooperation!

4.4 Instructions for blood sampling

1. Keep the specimen handling area clean and free of dust
2. Use only the supplies provided by the study responsible
3. Prepare the volunteer for phlebotomy, following your normal protocol, using alcohol to disinfect the collection site. Do not use solvent or other disinfectant products.
4. Fill completely the tubes to avoid the risk of haemolysis
5. After removing the tubes, invert them gently several times in order to mix the sample with the additive.
6. Sample treatment:
 - Plasma: centrifuge the sample to separate plasma from the cellular fraction. Carefully transfer the plasma into the vial avoiding transfer of the cellular components of blood. Place the cap on the vial tightly.
 - Serum: allow the sample to clot for at least 30 minutes but no more than 3 hours. Centrifuge the sample to separate serum from the cellular fraction. Carefully transfer the serum into the vial avoiding transfer of the cellular components of blood. Place the cap on the vial tightly.
7. Keep the samples vertically in the fridge at +4°C (max +10°C) until their transport according to the instructions defined in the *D.7.2 "Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands"*